

Gender and Power: A Focused Group Discussion

Dr Rey TY

Department of Peace Studies, International College, Payap University, Thailand

reyty4@gmail.com

Orcid: 0000-0002-9258-0318

ABSTRACT

Notwithstanding the advancement made in gender equality, women still face challenges in society, principally in terms of power dynamics. Women frequently face discrimination. The purpose of this paper was to explore the factors that contribute to empowerment and how these factors can be reinforced to advance gender and social equality. This article responds to the following research questions: 1) What are the sources of power? 2) What are the factors that contribute to empowerment? And 3) What strategies can be executed to promote empowerment? This study examines prior research on gender and power dynamics, including the challenges faced by women and the impact of gender discrimination and harassment. This paper used a qualitative research design, specifically a focused group discussion (FGD). The data collected were analyzed utilizing thematic analysis with a view to categorizing common themes and patterns. The findings of this work provided insights into the factors that contribute to empowerment with a view to promoting gender and social equality. This article contributed to the prevailing literature on gender and power dynamics, offering practical recommendations for promoting women's and social empowerment. The findings of this research are germane to communities, employers, decision makers, and women's advocacy groups.

Keywords: Gender, Empowerment, Human Agency, Oppression, Structural Constraints

1. CHAPTER 1 – INTRODUCTION

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite progress in gender equality, women still face countless challenges. These challenges include oppression and power dynamics in relation to men as well as in the larger social context. The social contexts include, among others, the household, academic institutions, places of worship, and the workplace. There is clearly a relationship between gender and power.

1.2 Research Questions

Based on the foregoing problem statement, this article responded to the following queries:

1.2.1 What are sources of power?

1.2.2 What are the factors that contribute to empowerment?

1.2.3 What strategies can be implemented to promote empowerment?

1.3. Purpose of the Study

In response to the research questions stated above, the purpose of this article was to expound on the sources of power, identify the factors that promote empowerment, and lay down strategies against oppression and for empowerment.

2. CHAPTER 2 – LITERATURE REVIEW

Note that social norms about gender roles are changing rapidly in societies in many parts of the world, while there are others that resist change. This article dealt with concepts and themes explored in previous research on gender, power dynamics, and factors that contribute to oppression and empowerment. They include studies in anthropology, law, political science, and public medicine. These pieces of prior literature dealt with the following in alphabetical order: education, equality, gender, hegemony, human agency, oppression, patriarchy, power dynamics, privilege, social justice, structural constraints. These concepts were woven to form a storyline regarding the use of human agency to veer away from the structural constraints of oppression to empowerment. Political economy ties everything together: interweaving the economy, politics, and culture (Polanyi, 2001). See Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Political Economy as the Overarching Framework

Source: Author of This Article

For this paper, sex refers to the biological differences in chromosomes, while gender relates to the expected social roles of women and men in different points in time in each society. Structures and agency are twins. Structural constraints impede the equality of the status between women and men. They include class status, culture, gender roles, hegemony, patriarchy, privilege, and power dynamics. Human agency can be utilized to advance the equality of the status between women and men, as a result of which, gender empowerment, gender justice, and social justice are promoted (World Bank, 2014).

By gender is mean the social construction of the expected comporment, roles, characteristics, and actions that are considered proper for women and men in a given time or historical context and space or social context (Jewkes et al., 2015). For example, women are expected to be caring and emotive, whereas men are projected to be breadwinners who are fearless and without feeling. Patriarchy refers to institutions and unequal system of relations in society wherein male persons hold primary economic, political, ideological, cultural, social, moral authority, privilege, dominance, control, and power over women (Guy-Evans, 2023). To illustrate, women are paid less than men for equal work and men overwhelmingly hold more leadership positions than women. In short, it is a systemic gender oppression marked by the practice and culture that promotes comprehensive material and e male dominance (API.gov, 2023; Guy-Evans, 2023). In general, culture means the attitudes, behaviors, beliefs, customs, expected roles, traditions, values, and material objects related to one group or one society in different points in time.

Though societies in the world are changing, men in general still have the hegemonic position of privilege and power. Hegemony is defined as the dominance of one group, in this case, men, over another, in this case, women, through long-held practice and traditional culture of patriarchy. By privilege is meant the entitlements and advantageous positions that men possess on the basis of their sex and expected gender roles in society. Power means the capacity to impact, stimulate, or regulate the conduct of others, ranging from encouragement to the use of brute power. By power dynamics we mean the ways wherein power is distributed and exercised between the sexes and the expected gender roles in society.

Under patriarchy, women experience oppression in the economic, political, cultural, normative, and discursive realms. As a result, these systemic restraints and structures hinder the full development of women. They are systematically oppressed, sidelined, subjugated, and deprived, and underprivileged. Therefore, patriarchy and the resultant gender inequality need to be addressed so that social justice can be attained (Fal-Dutra Santos, 2019).

In general, the power dynamics in society is such that the oppression of women is linked directly to the privilege and power of men. In addition, the class, color, and other social statuses of women likely affect the status of women. Social status refers to the rank that a person holds in relation to others in society, with the corresponding responsibilities and rights. (APA, 2023). Class status refers to the economic position one holds in terms of type of profession and level of income, for instance, landlords, peasants, workers, or capitalists. Other statuses that a person can have include, minority or majority, color, rural or urban, and the like. Thus, women with complex intersectional identities can experience multiple oppression (Crenshaw, 1991, 1996, 2023).

Gender-transformative actions are needed to advance gender justice (Meyers, 2002). By gender justice is meant the equality and equity of women and men in all fields of human endeavor, where women and men jointly take part on equal terms in envisioning, formulating, and implementing policies, processes, and decision making which affect society. The purpose of gender justice is to address both the institutionalized and systemic causes of the marginalization of women with a view to usher in a society in which discrimination is eliminated and all have equal access to economic prospects, material resources, and rule-making power. By overcoming constraints in the social system and social structures, privileges

are transformed into rights (ECLA, 2020). Education, training, mentorship, consciousness raising, and networking not only of and among women but equally importantly of men and among the sexes are necessary to promote gender equality (Karam, 2023). Clearly, gender, justice, and empowerment are directly related (Fielding-Miller et al., 2020). For an integrated summary of the literature above, see Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: From Structural Constraints of Oppression to Human Agency of Empowerment

Source: Author of This Article

3. CHAPTER 3 – METHODOLOGY

This paper used a qualitative research design. The research philosophy for this paper was based on the material conditions about which participants engaged in an interpretivist exercise. The research paradigm was social constructivism, as the people involved in this exercise took part in developing their ideas, based upon their lived experiences. For this reason, the research approach was dialectical, according to which the objective social reality and experiences of the people who were involved in the exercise shared their subjective reflections and ideas on the structural constraints on gender roles as well as on the capacity of human agency for social transformation of gender roles. The research collaborators were from diverse cultural, national, professional, and religious backgrounds.

The research site was a village in the countryside in northern Thailand. The population of this research included the residents of northern Thailand. The qualitative sampling was non-random purposive, and convenience sampling, based on those who volunteered to join and participate in this event. The research data collection methods included plenary workshop, focused group discussions (FGD), and share-pair dialogue, which were the sources of data that served as inputs for this article. The time horizon was limited to a one-day whole-day activity.

The unit of analysis of this research comprised the data gathered from individuals about their viewpoints regarding gender roles in the family, community, and their professions in society at large. The levels of analysis included 1) micro-level: the individual participants, 2) meso-level: their relationship with the community and their professions, and 3) macro-level: the society at large.

Data analysis was based on data coding, data organization, categorization, and thematic analysis. As a co-producer of knowledge, the author of this article interpreted the data from the activities from his own perspective. Data interpretation led to the development of a storyline. Member checking and triangulation of different materials were the sources of the credibility and confirmability of the findings. Note, however, that significant as the findings were, this research did not make claims regarding the transferability of the implications of the study to other contexts, as the sources of data are from a limited number of people with a limited diversity of backgrounds. The website of the retreat center, personal notes, photographed documentation of the event notes, debriefing, and publicly published reflections were used for triangulation of data. Consistency of the findings was based upon the documented process and saturation of the data. As for ethics, all participants to the event were unnamed to ensure their anonymity and to protect their privacy. See Figure 3 below.

<p>Research Philosophy: Materialism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Design: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative Case Study 	<p>Research Paradigm</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dialectical Objective Realism and Social Constructivism of Subjective Views 	<p>Data Collection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plenary Workshop, Focused Group Discussion, & Share-Pair Dialogue
<p>Data Analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coding, Categorization, and Thematic Analysis 	<p>Data Interpretation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storyline in a Grounded Theory 	<p>Research Site</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Northern Thailand
<p>Sampling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative, Non-Random, Convenience 	<p>Credibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Member Check & Triangulation 	<p>Consistency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documented Process & Data Saturation

Figure 3: Research Methodology of This Research

Source: Author of This Article

4. CHAPTER 4 – FINDINGS

4.1 What Are the Sources of Power?

To respond to this query, basic information about the focused group discussion was documented here. The event from which the data for this article was culled was the workshop on anti-oppression. It took place in a retreat center in a remote village in northern Thailand. The activities took place for one whole day on Tuesday, February 7, 2023. The activities included plenary workshop discussions, focused group discussion, and rotating share-pair with different partners throughout the day. All in all, there were eight international participants, one Thai facilitator, and local staff members: one who served as the driver of the van that shuttled everyone roundtrip from the university to the site of the event as well as the in-house kitchen staff members who prepared the meals for the whole day at the venue in the village. See Table 1 below:

Table-1: Participants in the Gender and Power Focused Group Discussion

Number of Participants	Countries of Origin	Biological Sex
1	India	F
2	Myanmar	M x 2
1	Philippines	F
1	Philippines	M
1	Thailand	F
1	Thailand	M
1	U.S.A.	F
1	U.S.A.	M
1	Vietnam	F
Total: 10	Total: 6 Countries	F = 5; M = 5

Source: Author of This Article

The program was integrative, as it seeks to situate the individual in a larger social context for the purpose of bringing about social transformation. The members of this group were composed of women and men who were of diverse national, cultural, and religious heritage and origins. The facilitator of this gathering was a Buddhist feminist activist. For this round of activities,

her was grounded in the core values of feminism and social activism. These principles are enacted through mutual respect, diversity, consultation, community building, power sharing, structural violence as the root cause of social problems, unlearning internalized patriarchy, experiential learning, simplicity, as well as the linkage between personal practice and social change.

The sharing of ideas during the plenary workshop revealed that there are several steps in anti-oppression as well as for empowerment. The first step is self-awareness. The second step is diverse and inclusive groups working together. The third step is social transformation. The group engaged in an exercise in power analysis. Power analysis was conducted among individuals, including examining the positionality of marginalized groups. Participants noted that power plays a dual role, as it can be both a source of discord as well as the basis of transformation. During the whole day event, participants identified the sources of power that I as an individual, we, individuals, groups, institutions, states, and corporations possess.

Personal power is based upon one's position in three realms. The first is one's position in the family and clan. The second is one's position in the community, which includes residence, religion, and volunteer work. The third is one's position in one's profession, livelihood, associations, and organizations. Each person had very different positionality in the family, community, and society at large. For instance, one participant had zero power in the family, high level of power in the community for volunteer service, and almost zero power in the place of work. Another person had the opposite levels of power in these three spheres of human endeavor.

From the lively sharing of ideas in the plenum, the sources of oppression and power were identified. They are two sides of the same coin. Access to them or having the socially preferred attributes increases one's power. Denied access to them or not having the socially preferred attributes increases one's oppression. These sources include in alphabetical order the following: abilities, age, class, color, culture, education, ethnicity, experiences, gender, information access, institutions, intelligence, knowledge, networks, positions, race, relationships, sex, skills, and weapons possession. Organized differently, sources of power include access to decision-making positions, access to opportunities, access to resources, economic independence, educational attainment, knowledge base, networks, and social influence.

4.2 What Are the Factors that Contribute to Empowerment?

Power and oppression go together, but in opposite directions. The power relates to the underlying elements, conditions, and influences. Power can be either restraining or liberating. Accepting structural constraints or using human agency to overcome them affect our choices, decisions, freedom, health, liberty, life, opportunities, plans, rights, security, status, and wealth.

The participants agreed that they do not have to accept structural constraints. Rather, they have the human agency for social change. With human agency, people can overcome constraints, difficulties, fears, hegemony, impediments, injustices, structures, and violence.

4.3 What Strategies Can be Implemented to Promote Empowerment?

Empowerment refers to intentional actions. Based on the results of the one-day focused group discussion, there are several factors that promote empowerment. They include advocacy, coaching, collaboration, education, engagement, gender mainstreaming in organizations, leadership development, mentoring, providing safe and inclusive work space, recognition, representation, rewards, supportive culture, supportive policies, teamwork, and training. Empowerment comes in three forms: power over, power sharing, and power within. We need to have power over cultural constraints, meaning making, and patriarchy. We need to practice power sharing: community building; partnership, as well as supporting and helping others. To have power within, we need to have acceptance, assurance, confidence, courage, creativity, faith, flexibility, gratitude, hope, inner strength, integrity, joy, laughter, patience, resilience, understanding, and wisdom. See Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Grounded Theory of Empowerment

Source: Author of This Article based on the FGD Output

CONCLUSION

In summary, empowerment is not only for women or men. Empowerment is for all. In summary, this paper identified 1) the sources of power, 2) factors that promote empowerment, and 3) strategies for empowerment. This paper addressed the importance of studying gender and empowerment in today's world. It explored the implications of actions that promote gender empowerment in society. It provided actionable points in the form of strategies for social intervention that yields gender empowerment in different contexts. This research highlights the data outcomes that structural constraints and human agency that links gender and power.

There are some key lessons learned from the focused group discussion. One, offer an inclusive forum in which women and men of diverse backgrounds can interrelate with one another in the spirit of mutual respect, mutual understanding, and mutual benefit. Two, afford time and a venue in which personal reflection and growth can flourish in a supportive atmosphere. Three, increase knowledge, skills, and values that encourage work for positive social change; Four, shape a caring community from diverse and intersectional backgrounds with a shared commitment to construct positive social change.

Who cares about gender empowerment? This topic is significant to individuals, both women and men, communities, and whole societies. This article explored the economic, political, and cultural impact of gender oppression and the advantages of gender empowerment. It engendered the cognizance of gender empowerment and nurtured a sense of urgency in the necessity to address gender discrepancies.

So what? In this research, there are implications to several stakeholders. The paper scrutinized views about gender relations in society which contribute to our comprehension of gender and power, underscoring their impact on individuals, the community, and society at large.

Now what? Going beyond merely the conceptual level, this paper shed light on the tasks that need to be done to promote gender empowerment. Individuals, activists, community organizers, educators, organizations, policy makers, trainers can play pro-active roles in consciousness raising with a view to stimulating actions that advance gender empowerment. As this research relied on a few research collaborators, there are still gaps in the production of knowledge that can be filled. Other researchers and scholars can gather more co-producers of

knowledge either for deeper insights from qualitative findings or more generalizable inferences from quantitative research that relies on meta datasets. Step by step, we are committed to continuing our efforts for collaborative efforts with the purpose of achieving meaningful transformation of society that promotes gender empowerment.

REFERENCES

- APA. (2023). Socioeconomic status [Psychology Topics]. *American Psychological Association*. <https://www.apa.org/topics/socioeconomic-status>
- API.gov. (2023). Patriarch & power. *Asia Pacific Institute on Gender-Based Violence*. <https://www.api-gbv.org/about-gbv/our-analysis/patriarchy-power/>
- Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color. *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), 1241. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>
- Crenshaw, K. (1996). *Critical Race Theory: The Key Writings That Formed the Movement*. The New Press.
- Crenshaw, K. (2023). *On Intersectionality: Essential Writings*. The New Press.
- ECLA. (2020, January 28). Calls Are Made to Overcome the Structural Constraints of Gender Inequality, Foster Women's Autonomy in the Current Regional Economic Context, and Transform Privileges into Rights. *Economic Commission for Latin America*. <https://www.cepal.org/en/pressreleases/calls-are-made-overcome-structural-constraints-gender-inequality-foster-womens>
- Fal-Dutra Santos, R. (2019, July 18). Challenging patriarchy: Gender equality and humanitarian principles. *ICRC*. <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/challenging-patriarchy-gender-equality-and-humanitarian-principles>
- Fielding-Miller, R., Hatcher, A. M., Wagman, J., Swendeman, D., & Upadhyay, U. D. (2020). Gender, justice and empowerment: Creating the world we want to see. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 22(sup1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691058.2020.1736843>
- Guy-Evans, O. (2023, April 20). Patriarchal Society According to Feminism. *Simply Sociology*. <https://simplysociology.com/patriarchal-society-feminism-definition.html>
- Jewkes, R., Morrell, R., Hearn, J., Lundqvist, E., Blackbeard, D., Lindegger, G., Quayle, M., Sikweyiya, Y., & Gottzén, L. (2015). Hegemonic masculinity: Combining theory and practice in gender interventions. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 17(sup2), 112–127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691058.2015.1085094>
- Karam, A. (2023). Education as the Pathway towards Gender Equality [United Nations]. *U.N. Chronicle*. <https://www.un.org/en/chronicle/article/education-pathway-towards-gender-equality>
- Meyers, D. T. (2002). Gender Identity and Women's Agency: Culture, Norms, and Internalized Oppression Revisited. In D. T. Meyers, *Gender in the Mirror* (1st ed., pp. 3–29). Oxford University Press New York. <https://doi.org/10.1093/0195140419.003.0001>
- Polanyi, K. (2001). *The great transformation: The political and economic origins of our time* (Second Beacon Paperback edition). Beacon Press.
- World Bank. (2014). *Voice and agency: Empowering women and girls for shared prosperity*. World Bank. https://www.worldbank.org/content/dam/Worldbank/document/Gender/Voice_and_agency_LOWRES.pdf